

SPONTANEOUS SUBARACHNOID HEMORRHAGE: EARLY PREDICTION AND ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS FOR SHUNT DEPENDENT HYDROCEPHALUS

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Background: Hydrocephalus is a well-known sequel of spontaneous subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) caused by aneurysm rupture (AR). It is still not clear what can reduce shunt dependency.

Object: The present study aimed to investigate imaging status, location of the AR, neurological status and treatments applied, associated with consecutive shunt dependent hydrocephalus (SDHC) and functional outcomes after SAH.

Methods: A retrospective review was conducted in 215 patients with SAH who underwent surgical clipping or endovascular treatment in the Clinical center of Vojvodina, Novi Sad Serbia, during a 5 year period. Relevant clinical and radiographic data were analyzed with concerning the risk of shunt dependency after different treatments. All variables including age, sex, WFNS scale, Fisher grade (FG), acute hydrocephalus (AH), intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH), angiographic vasospasm (AV), type of treatment, functional outcomes (using Glasgow outcome score-GOS) and location of AR were retrospectively collected. Incidence of SDHC was analyzed using each treatment modality. Independent tests and multivariate odds ratios from logistic regression analyses were calculated after stratification.

Results: 237 patients were registered as having had an SAH caused by a ruptured aneurysm of whom 63 (26.5%) required permanent ventricular shunting in our series. Treatments included craniotomy and clipping in 123 patients and endovascular coil embolization in 114 patients. The institutional series revealed ruptured vertebrobasilar aneurysm, AH, FG, WFNS scale, IVH and AV as significant risk factors ($P < .05$) associated with SDHC on univariate and multivariate analysis. Patients who did not receive a VPS at discharge had higher GOS scores and were more likely to be functionally independent and to return to work 6 months after SAH.

Conclusions: A significantly higher rate of shunt dependency was observed for poor initial neurological status, thick SAH with presence of initial IVH, AV, AH as well as with the location of the AR. In this study comparing two modalities for treatment of aneurysm, endovascular or microsurgical means, there was no difference in shunt dependency after SAH. Patients in whom SDHC does not develop after SAH tend to have improved long-term functional outcomes. By understanding these factors related to development of SDHC and results, it is expected that management of aneurysmal SDHC caused by SAH will result in a better prognosis.

Key words: Spontaneous subarachnoid hemorrhage, Aneurysm rupture, Hydrocephalus, Ventriculoperitoneal shunt